

THE USAGE OF SYNONYMY IN TRANSPORT TERMINOLOGY

Narzullayeva Nigina Murodullo qizi

Master's student of the faculty „Comparative linguistics
and linguistic translation”

Contact: +998900816610

niginanarzullayeva30@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13837386>

Abstract: The given publication work is aimed at analysing the usage of synonymy in the field of transportation. By the help of the article importance of synonymy in order to increase transportation vocabulary rate is studied.

Key words: transportation terms, terminological synonymy, One-component terms-synonyms, Multicomponent synonymous terms.

Terminological synonymy is based on several factors, among them the following can be distinguished:

1. As a rule, formation and terminologies in the development stage have many synonyms. This can be explained by extra linguistic factors such as the internationalization of science. In addition, the same phenomenon scientists from different countries or scientific schools and considered by specialists, as a result of which it receives a different name. The terminological system of transport under study is in the development stage because then it will definitely be variable.

2. The essence of the event is the most accurate the need to move also creates synonyms in terminology, because each of the participants (scientists, experts) tend to emphasize a certain aspect of such a phenomenon.

3. Borrowings from other terms, as well as general vocabulary. It should be noted that the traffic in the studied English and Uzbek languages. There are many synonyms in the terminology of this production field from many other fields - economy, management, transport lexical units from related fields of knowledge that appeared due to as a rule, it also has its own synonyms.

Now we want look at the phenomenon of synonymy in this terminological system:

1. One-component terms-synonyms, noun + noun. At the same time, synonyms are absolute strings and synonymous terms have different meanings rows containing can be distinguished. First looking at absolute synonyms Examples of this are the following terms in British English and American English. For example, railway (Br. Eng.) – railroad (Am. Eng.) – temir yo'l; vagon

(Br. Eng.) – car (Am.Eng.) – temir yo'l vagonlari; lorry (Br. Eng.) – truck (Am. Eng.) – yuk mashinasi

Although they are considered **absolute synonyms**, there is a slight difference. Truck in general cargo considered as a car, that is, any type of lorry term is heavy, overweight applied to trucks. Also, the terms are close, but one in specialized literature that does not have the same meaning, but at the same time (that is, in the term system) there are several synonymous strings, for example: agreement –contract - shartnoma.

In the text of the same contract (again transport within the framework of logistics) both of these terms can be used, i.e. they can be absolute synonyms. But in legal practice, of course, there is a difference, we can say that the contract, as a rule, is written, approved exists in the form and an agreement is a verbal agreement:

When an agreement is reached, the ship is fixed [Liu, 2012: 387].

Kelishuvga erishilganda, kema ijaraga beriladi.

This is why many organisations prefer a more formal arrangement, with a written contract setting out the obligations of each party [Waters, 2003: 45].

Shuning uchun ko'plab tashkilotlar har bir tomonning majburiyatlarini belgilaydigan yozma shartnomadan ko'ra rasmiyroq kelishuvni afzal ko'radi.

The second group of synonymous terms with one component are terms with different meanings is represented by lines with colors: **cargo - freight - load**. We translate the terms into Uzbek in the same way, but the cargo is water or air is used for transport by (i.e. sea or air transport), while freight used for land transportation, for example, in a truck.

way – road – path – route – yo'l.

The term “way” has the broadest meaning, but “road” means a plot of land specially organized for transportation, “route” means a predetermined path, a route.

2) Multicomponent synonymous terms are the most common among terms the two component terms are synonyms. In this case, the following is effectiveness models can be distinguished:

Model 1: noun + noun → noun + noun.

container ship → container vessel – konteyner tashaydigan kema;

agent surcharge → agent fee –agent komissiyasi;

branch line → branch railway –temir yo'l liniyasi;

delivery specification → delivery terms –tovarlarni yetkazib berish shartlari;

dock traffic → port bound traffic –portdagi tirbandlik;

land transport → surface transport –yer usti transporti;
truck dock → truck platform –avtomobillarni yuklash va tushirish platformasi.
It can be assumed that it will be further filled with, this is the field of knowledge being studied allows for a more accurate and multifaceted definition of events and processes.

The study of synonyms is of practical importance because, in our opinion, a series. The fact that synonyms work is recorded in the dictionary of study and transport terms shows the need to achieve. We can conclude that analyzing the synonymy rate in transportation need to be studied further.

Reference:

1. Macmillan English Dictionary. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc., 2002. – 1692 p
2. Waters, D. Logistics: An Introduction to Supply Chain Management. – N.Y.: Palgrave, Macmillan, 2003. –364 p
3. Lakoff, G. The contemporary theory of metaphor // Metaphor and thought. Second ed / ed. by A. Ortony. – New York: CUP, 1993. – P.202-251.
4. Mirzahmedova. X.Turk tilidagi transport terminlarini struktur tuzilishi va yasalishi muammosi. 2018. – b. 17-19
5. Ҳожиев А. Тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати.- Т.: ЎЗМЭ, 2002. – 104 б

